

THE STUDY OF LINGUISTIC TERMS IN WORLD LINGUISTICS

Guzal Tilovova Rustamovna

Teacher of the University of Economics and Pedagogy

Annotation: The article deals with significant information according to the study of linguistic terms in world linguistics. On the other hand, definition and main peculiarities of the terms which are often used in linguistics were noted.

Key words: *imagination sets, non-linguistic communication, speech-sounds, Productivity, Synchronic linguistics, General Linguistics, Structural analysis.*

Human beings can communicate with each other. We are able to exchange knowledge, beliefs, opinions, wishes, threats, commands, thanks, promises, declarations, feelings – only our imagination sets limits. We can laugh to express amusement, happiness, or disrespect, we can smile to express amusement, pleasure, approval, or bitter feelings, we can shriek to express anger, excitement, or fear, we can clench our fists to express determination, anger or a threat, we can raise our eyebrows to express surprise or disapproval, and so on, but our system of communication before anything else is language. The first step towards a definition we can say that it is a system of communication-based upon words and the combination of words into sentences. Communication by means of language may be referred to as linguistic communication, the other ways mentioned above – laughing, smiling, shrieking, and so on – are types of non-linguistic communication. Most of all non-human species can exchange information, but none of them is known to have a system of communication with a complexity that in any way is comparable to language. Primarily, they communicate with non-linguistic means resembling our smiling, laughing, yelling, clenching of fists, and raising of eyebrows. Chimpanzees, gorillas, and orangutans can exchange different kinds of information by emitting different kinds of shrieks, composing their faces

in numerous ways, and moving their hands or arms in different gestures, but they do not have words and sentences[1]. By moving in certain patterns, bees are apparently able to tell their fellow workers where to find honey, but apparently not very much else. Birds sing different songs, whose main functions are to defend their territory or to attract a mate. Language – as defined above – is an exclusively human property.

Many definitions of language have been proposed. Henry Sweet, an English phonetician and language scholar, stated: “Language is the expression of ideas by means of speech-sounds combined into words. Words are combined into sentences, this combination answering to that of ideas into thoughts.” The American linguists Bernard Bloch and George L. Trager formulated the following definition: “A language is a system of arbitrary vocal symbols by means of which a social group cooperates.” Any succinct definition of language makes a number of presuppositions and begs a number of questions. The first, for example, puts excessive weight on “thought,” and the second uses “arbitrary” in a specialized, though legitimate, way Language is a means of communication that is used to transfer information, ideas, and feelings from one person to another. Language is also a system of communication based upon words and the combination of words into sentences. By using language, people can develop their knowledge and know about something. Cameron (2001:17), in applied linguistics over the last decades, it has been common to divide language into the four skills: Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing, and include grammar, vocabulary and phonology to them[2].

Productivity is a general term in linguistics referring to the limitless ability to use language— any natural language—to say new things. It is also known as open-endedness or creativity. The term productivity is also applied in a narrower sense to particular forms or constructions (such as affixes) that can be used to produce new instances of the same type. In this sense, productivity is most commonly discussed in connection with word-formation. "Humans are continually

creating new expressions and novel utterances by manipulating their linguistic resources to describe new objects and situations. This property is described as productivity (or 'creativity' or 'open-endedness') and it is linked to the fact that the potential number of utterances in any human language is infinite. Synchronic linguistics is one of the two main temporal dimensions of language study introduced by Saussure in his "Course in General Linguistics" (1916). The other is diachronic linguistics, which is the study of language through periods of time in history. The first looks at a snapshot of a language, and the other studies its evolution (like a frame of film vs. a movie). For example, analyzing the word order in a sentence in Old English only would be a study in synchronistic linguistics.

Linguistics is based on a theoretical as well as a descriptive study of language and is also interlinked with the applied fields of language studies and language learning, which entails the study of specific languages. Before the 20th century, linguistics evolved in conjunction with literary study and did not employ scientific methods[3]. Modern-day linguistics is considered a [science](#) because it entails a comprehensive, systematic, [objective](#), and precise analysis of all aspects of language – i.e., the [cognitive](#), the [social](#), the [cultural](#), the [psychological](#), the environmental, the biological, the literary, the grammatical, the [paleographical](#), and the [structural](#). Linguistics encompasses [many branches and subfields](#) that span both theoretical and practical applications. [Theoretical linguistics](#) (including traditional descriptive linguistics) is concerned with understanding the [universal](#) and [fundamental nature](#) of language and developing a general theoretical framework for describing it. [Applied linguistics](#) seeks to utilize the scientific findings of the study of language for practical purposes, such as developing methods of improving language education and literacy. Linguistic features may be studied through a variety of perspectives: [synchronically](#) (by describing the shifts in a language at a certain specific point of time) or [diachronically](#) (through the historical development of language over several

periods of time), in [monolinguals](#) or in [multilinguals](#), amongst children or amongst adults, in terms of how it is being learned or how it was acquired, as abstract objects or as cognitive structures, through written texts or through oral elicitation, and finally through mechanical data collection or through practical fieldwork.

Linguistics emerged from the field of [philology](#), of which some branches are more qualitative and holistic in approach. Today, philology and linguistics are now variably described as related fields, subdisciplines, or separate fields of language study but, by and large, linguistics can be seen as an umbrella term. The fundamental principle of humanistic linguistics, especially rational and [logical grammar](#), is that language is an invention created by people. A semiotic tradition of linguistic research considers language a [sign system](#) which arises from the interaction of meaning and form. The organisation of linguistic levels is considered computational. Linguistics is essentially seen as relating to [social](#) and [cultural studies](#) because different languages are shaped in [social interaction](#) by the [speech community](#). Frameworks representing the [humanistic](#) view of language include [structural linguistics](#), among others[4]. Structural analysis means dissecting each linguistic level: phonetic, morphological, syntactic, and discourse, to the smallest units. These are collected into inventories (e.g. phoneme, morpheme, lexical classes, phrase types) to study their interconnectedness within a hierarchy of structures and layers. Functional analysis adds to structural analysis the assignment of semantic and other functional roles that each unit may have. For example, a noun phrase may function as the subject or object of the sentence; or the [agent](#) or [patient](#).

[Functional linguistics](#), or functional grammar, is a branch of structural linguistics. In the humanistic reference, the terms [structuralism](#) and [functionalism](#) are related to their meaning in other [human sciences](#). The difference between formal and functional structuralism lies in the way that the two approaches explain why languages have the properties they have.

Functional [explanation](#) entails the idea that language is a tool for communication, or that communication is the primary function of language. Linguistic forms are consequently explained by an appeal to their functional value, or usefulness. Other structuralist approaches take the perspective that form follows from the inner mechanisms of the bilateral and multilayered language system.

Summing up all given facts above it should be noted that human language, that unique characteristic of our species, has been of interest throughout history and from the history we can discover some basic terms of linguistics. The scientific study of human language is called linguistics. A linguist, then, is not someone who speaks many languages (although many linguists do); such individuals are polyglots. A linguist is a scientist who investigates human language in all its facets, its structure, its use, its history, its place in society. The form and structure of the kinds of linguistic knowledge speakers possess is the concern of theoretical linguistics. This theory of grammar – the mental representation of linguistic knowledge – is what this textbook is about. But the field of linguistics is not limited to grammatical theory; it includes a large number of subfields, which is true of most sciences concerned with phenomena as complex as human language.

REFERENCES:

1. 5 Successful Goal-Setting Strategies for Language Learning, 2021 from: <https://www.reallearningacademy.com/5-successful-goal-setting-strategies-for-language-learning/>
2. Wang, H. (2018). Incorporating Personalized Learning into the Foreign Language Classroom. *English Language Teaching*, 11(7), 1-9.

